

THE IMPORTANCE OF TOYS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF A CHILD

Shodmonova Laylo O'ral qizi

f.f.n. Panjiyeva N.N

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Abstract. This paper shows the role of toys in children development. The paper focuses on its benefits which helps in child's development. The paper identifies the challenges in child's development. Toys plays an important role in child development. Toys helps in overall development of child, which may differ from person to person, culture to culture or generation to generation. The best experience of childhood which children enjoys is their playing time with toys. Different variety of toys help in different level of development of child for example educational toys helps children to play and learn simultaneously with one another in a fun way. It also helps in building their social interaction with other kids. It helps in child's physical mental social emotional and creative development also. Parents also encourage their child to choose appropriate toy.

Key words: Toys, Child Development, Specially Abled Children, Memory Games, Creative Development.

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ИГРУШЕК В РАЗВИТИИ РЕБЕНКА

Аннотация. В статье показана роль игрушек в развитии детей. В статье основное внимание уделяется его преимуществам, которые помогают в развитии ребенка. В статье обозначены проблемы в развитии ребенка. Игрушки играют важную роль в развитии ребенка. Игрушки помогают в общем развитии ребенка, которое может отличаться от человека к человеку, от культуры к культуре или от поколения к поколению. Лучшие впечатления детства, которые доставляют детям радость, — это игры с игрушками. Различные игрушки помогают на разном уровне развития ребенка, например, развивающие игрушки помогают детям играть и учиться одновременно друг с другом в увлекательной игровой форме. Это также помогает в построении социального взаимодействия с другими детьми. Это также помогает в физическом, умственном, социальном, эмоциональном и творческом развитии ребенка. Родители также поощряют своего ребенка выбирать подходящую игрушку.

Ключевые слова: игрушки, развитие ребенка, дети с особыми способностями, игры на память, творческое развитие.

Toys play as an integral part in the learning process and child individual development also depends on the toy chosen. With the growth and development their need for a specific toy will change as their age their interest level and their abilities. The selection of toys depends on child behavior and their interest some may choose puzzle games memory games manipulative games and other board games which can be played indoors. These type of games can be played alone or with a volunteer or with a parent or with a small group of friends. Same way outdoor games like basketball badminton cricket etc requires physical strength and specific number of players. Following are the various developments inner child which is facilitated by playing with toys which are given below:

Emotional or Social Development

Many lessons for living in the society can be easily learnt by playing with the toys. Social development is very crucial element in child's development. Social development includes self-discipline, sharing, cooperation, togetherness and empathy. While playing they can share their thoughts without any restrictions in their group. Children learn to cooperate by playing with each other by sharing turns. It helps to realize their potential and give satisfaction of success. It ends in manage their emotions values and able to interpret the world around them.

Physical Development

Children love toys which involves physical movement such as coloring, cutting, dressing up their dolls and playing with color coordinated games. Toys which involves activities like coloring, matching cut outs, art and craft related toys, placing cut outs on the board etc. involves fine motor skills that helps in development of small muscle coordination and helps in development of hand-eye coordination. Playing with activity toys strengthens their physical development.

Cognitive Development

Cognitive skills involve conscious intellectual activity, thinking, reasoning or remembering that can be developed by playing with toys. It helps child to perceive to intuit in the process of gaining or acquiring knowledge with the help of toys. Toys like building blocks, pattern blocks, some connecting games which involve experiments to make designs, all these type of games make their thinking process stronger, they learn to invent, construct, use their creative thinking and develop problem solving skills. Many games help in developing mathematical skills such as counting matching patterns and classifications. It is a proven fact that by playing with more and more games, child can have better creative thinking and can become better problem solver.

Educational Development

Children are born with a desire to learn and playing with toys, encourage them do it. It helps in enhancement of knowledge of developing concepts, problem solving skills etc. at the initial stage of learning the child learns different shapes sizes colors numbers pictures textures with the help of toys. Toys gives a means to explore experiment with things and furnish with new information. It gives a pathway for future life to next level of schooling. Role playing with toys helps them to build creative imagination powers together with builds good communication skills. It helps to develop a sense of responsibility which is required for school and future life.

Moral Development

Toy plays a significant role for moral education of the child. While playing child get to know what is right and wrong. Child learns to play fairly, honestly and truthfully. They learn to play with the true sportsmanship. They learn to play for winning and face the failure with grace, which eventually help them learn to face the challenges but still be persistent to resolve it.

Creative Development

Children get excited to explore new world which gives new experience, toys give the best platform to imagine. Toys like blocks construction toys crayons etc. are the tools for creative growth. At the early age child has natural curiosity to explore to find many things. Kids love to enact like adults. They do small role plays enacting their parents for their profession, driving, cooking, grocery, shopping etc.

Communication Skill Development

Toys that involves interaction provides benefit of encouraging child's social development. In the learning process of child's social development, communication plays the vital role that involves both listening and interacting with other people. There are toys and games that helps in building the communication skill from the early age. Playing Toys in small groups like neighbors or with parents encourages child to interact with each other in safe environment, without any inhibition.

Technological Development

Kids love doing different experiments at different stages of their growth. Toys that involve learning via experiment that includes telescopes, solar system sets, microscope, chemistry sets, physics sets, etc. all these helps them to strengthen thinking skills. At the initial stage kids start with basic model building toys to advanced assembling toys with their expanding knowledge and the level of interest.

Challenges in Child Development

Selection of correct toy for a child as per the age or as per any difficult situation or specialabilities which child is facing, is a tough decision for parents. There is different level of special abilities which a child can face during the learning process.

Visual Skills

Children with visual impairment enjoy more with the toys that they can feel textures, which can make sounds, which they feel with their vibrations, toys that can give some sensory stimulation. Child with reasonable visual weakness can enjoys toys that emit bright lights. Toys plays a vital role in learning process for the children facing visual challenges. At the early stage of learning these toys encourage them to have playful learning with minimal difficulties.

Hearing Skills

Children facing hearing disorder/discomfort should choose toys which has lights or some visuals in it, toy should include volume controls, can have some textures or some other unique features that is appropriate for them. Toys that nurture thinking abilities such as puzzles, board matching games etc. should also be considered for older kids

Motor Skills

Children who face challenges in motor skills struggle with lack of both gross motor skills which includes jumping, balancing or running. They may face problem in holding pencils or putting laces in the strings through holes etc. Children with motor impairments do face trouble in movement of hands or legs. There are various means which schools for especially abled kids use in their development process. Toys having suction cups or magnets gives stability in terms of holding it. Light weight toys requires less strength will be much easier for children to handle. Toys made up of unbreakable materials or soft foams rubber should be used.

Cognitive Skills

Cognitive development means how a child thinks, explore and figure out things. it is the development of knowledge, particular skill, problem solving which helps a child to think about and understand the world around them. Simple jigsaws puzzle and memory games, encourage stacking and telling jokes and riddles etc. can be used at early age. Child can frequently play games with simple rules.

To a certain level extend playing with certain toys can help them in building the cognitive skills.

Learning Skills

Learning is a neurological condition in which child face difficulties in understanding the meaning of words or sometimes they interchange the meaning with one another. Toys helps them to understand or enhance their thinking ability, they will be able understand the cause and effect of the problem educational toys can help them in dealing with these challenges. Educational toys like Puzzles, board games, number games etc can improve their logical reasoning ability.

Categories of Toys

Real-life and Nurturing

Doll family, doll house, baby bottle, variety of puppets, animal families, cars, money, cash, register, kitchen food, medical kit, phone, etc.

Acting-out, Aggressive, Scary Toys (or not?)

oBop bag, toy soldiers, guns (colored plastic-not real looking!), scary/aggressive puppets and animals (alligator, shark, etc), rubber knife, foam sword, handcuffs, etc.

Creative expression and emotional release:

Sand, water, paints, craft materials, clay, musical instruments, magic wand, dress-up clothes, etc

Conclusion

Parents always want to help their children to achieve their full potential, they generally like to ignore the special ability discussion. However, kids gain most of the knowledge when they are relaxed and enjoying in the safe environment of home or the area which their parents define best for them. A child can memorize lot of information but the retention or better understanding of the same will happen with hands on experience only, i.e. to know and understand how really things work. Hence, the selection of right toy for the right age, environment and encouragement to conquer the world is an utmost requirement for the child's development.

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